

Further developments in the dynamics of female labour-force participation

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Abstract Papers attempting to explain female labour-force participation either do not include women-specific variables or lack a proper dynamic specification. In this paper, we estimate a dynamic equation for female labour-force participation in OECD countries from 1980 to 2007, taking into account several sets of variables. Moreover, we use our model to predict the results for 2007-2011, and we find that our model adjusts quite well to the actual data even with regard to the out-sample observations during the ongoing recession. In order to gain further insight concerning the interpretation and robustness of the equation, it is then compared to a similar equation for males. Our results show that real wage is one of the most relevant variables for female participation. Thus our specification could also be useful to endogenise labour-force participation for a macro labour market framework such as that of Layard et al. [1991, rev. 2005]. However, women's preferences, the overall level of education, and other structural factors are also important.

Keywords labour-force participation · gender · GMM

JEL-Classification: J13, J21, J82

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1 Introduction

The growing participation and employment of women in the labour market is certainly one of the salient traits of the evolution of OECD economies in the last two decades. Nevertheless, maintaining this increase is still an important policy objective in OECD countries. Thus one of the main aims of Europe 2020 for growth in the European Union (EU) is the increase in female employment and participation rates.¹ Accordingly, it is important to acquire knowledge on the factors influencing female participation in order to reach this target. Achieving this aim is not easy since labour-force participation rates are influenced by supply and demand factors. Female participation may be low because women do not wish to enter into the labour market, or because there are relatively few jobs available to them. In the former case low participation rates are explained by women's preferences, in the latter by employers preferences and labour-market institutions.

Several authors have tried to single out factors that influence female labour-force participation. Most of these papers analyse its relationship with fertility and/or education. In other words, they seem to consider that women's preferences constitute the main explanation for their low rate of participation in the labour market. Recently, Jaumotte [2004] and Genre et al. [2010] have pointed out the importance of labour-market institutions for explaining female labour-force participation. These authors, however, do not take into account the dynamics in the labour market. In this paper, we examine the specific factors that influence female labour-force participation but, following the econometric tradition begun with Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969], we estimate a dynamic model. In this context, it is also interesting to note that recent labour market analyses such as Layard et al. [1991, rev. 2005] and Mortensen and Pissarides [1994] estimate dynamic equations, considering labour-force participation as exogenous. Thus our specification could also be useful to endogenize labour-force participation in such a framework. In effect, while our main aim is to shed some light on the factors affecting female labour-force participation in OECD countries, we also estimate an equation for male labour-force participation. This is done with a view to assessing the robustness and significance of our results for female labour-force participation, but it also has some independent interest of its own. We do not intend to explain the effects of the recent economic crisis on female labour-force participation; rather, our aim is to look at the structural factors influencing female participation. Our period of analysis is 1980-2007, although we also outline some predictive exercises for the 2007-2010 period.

¹ The objectives of the EU are to become a smart, sustainable and inclusive economy. Thus, one of the targets is to reach a 75% employment rate for women and men aged 20-64 by 2020. In countries such Ireland and Spain this rate did not reach 60% for women in 2010 and in Italy it did not reach 50%. In the past, similar benchmarks had already been set by the so-called Lisbon Strategy, using a rather dubious effect. See Destefanis and Mastromatteo [2012] for a recent analysis.

This paper is divided into several sections. In section 2, we survey the literature to find the factors that could influence female participation. In section 3, we present our database and the empirical framework, basically a dynamic panel model. The results are shown and commented on in section 4. Finally, in section 5 we draw some brief conclusions.

2 Background

Traditional literature considers the decision to participate in the labour market as an individual decision. Therefore female labour-force participation is much more extensively studied at the micro than macro level. The structural microeconomic model for female labour supply decisions is framed in the life-cycle models. The joint nature of fertility and female labour supply decisions has long been recognised and introduced both in static [Cain and Dooley, 1976, Schultz, 1990] and dynamic models [Moffitt, 1984, Hotz and Miller, 1988]. Moreover, the first empirical study to have incorporated endogenous experience in addition to fertility and schooling is the research by Eckstein and Wolpin [1989]. By estimating a structural model they were able to distinguish the effect of work experience on wages from the effect on the disutility of employment. They found that disutility of work increases with experience but is compensated by a large positive estimated experience effect on wages, leading to positive state dependence. In more recent developments, Francesconi [2002] distinguishes between part-time and full-time employment, which affect wages and utility differently. The observed lower persistence in part-time employment is mainly due to the small own-experience effect on part-time earnings. Moreover, he found that part-time work during childbirth and childrearing years does not contribute to a substantial increase in lifetime utility in comparison to work interruption. Eckstein and Lifshitz [2011] compare a dynamic model based on Eckstein and Wolpin [1989] with static versions of the labour supply model. They maintain that the dynamic model provides a much better fit to the life-cycle employment pattern than a static version of the model or a standard static reduced form model [Heckman, 1979]. To our knowledge, a dynamic form for female labour-force participation has not been implemented in the macro framework. Nevertheless, for policy makers it is important to take into account spillovers and dynamics, and this requires a macro framework for their proper empirical assessment. The role of institutions may also be studied much more accurately in a cross-country framework, which almost inevitably implies the need to rely on macro estimates.

2.1 The basic model

To develop the basic specification we started out from the utility analysis (goods-leisure choice) of an individual in a competitive market [Lucas Jr and Rapping, 1969, Clark and Summers, 1982]. In this model, individuals choose

between spending time in leisure activities (l) or in paid work (L) to use their earnings to purchase goods (c). Nevertheless, this trade-off between current leisure and goods captures only one facet of the labour-supply decision: equally important are choices involving substitution with future goods (c^e) and leisure (l^e). Thus, individuals are assumed to maximize an intertemporal utility function of the form:

$$U = U(c_t, l_t, c^e, l^e) \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$p_t c_t + \frac{p^e}{1+r} \leq A_t + w_t L_t + \frac{w^e}{1+r} L^e \quad (2)$$

i.e. subject to the constraint that the present value of consumption cannot exceed the present value of income. Present values are computed using a nominal interest rate r . Moreover, individuals have an initial level of assets (A) which may be positive or negative, they are paid at a wage w and they consume goods at a price p . As a result, the solution to the maximization problem gives each of the decision variables (c , c^e , L , L^e) as a function not merely of their present wages (w) and prices (p) but also of their expectations of future nominal wages (w^e) and future prices (p^e), in addition to the interest rate r and the initial level of assets (A). In particular, the current labour-supply function would be:²

$$L_t = F\left(p, \frac{w^e}{(1+r)}, \frac{p^e}{(1+r)}, A_t\right) \quad (3)$$

Since this paper focuses on the participation decision, it could be easier to interpret the derivatives relative to the reservation wage, i.e. the minimum wage at which an individual will join the labour force (supply a positive amount of labour). Note that an interior maximum with positive participation will occur if the market wage w_t , exceeds the reservation wage (w_t^*). People will in general differ in their tastes, market opportunities as well as asset accumulation. Consequently, there will exist a joint distribution of market and reservation wages; the aggregate participation rate L^s is then given by:

$$L^s = \iint_{w_t > w_t^*} g(w_t, w_t^*) dw_t dw_t^* \quad (4)$$

where

$$w_t^* = f\left(p, \frac{w^e}{(1+r)}, \frac{p^e}{(1+r)}, A_t\right) \quad (5)$$

The derivative respect to current wage is expected to be positive, as contemporaneous increases in real wages raise the attractiveness of seeking work. The rest of the derivatives can be interpreted relative to the reservation wage; since leisure is a normal good, an increase in wealth, *ceteris paribus*, raises the reservation wage and as result, it causes a negative effect on the labour supply. Moreover, job opportunities come and go at random, depending to

² The function F is homogeneous of degree zero all its arguments.

some extent on individual search effort, the availability of jobs, and plain luck [Andolfatto, 1996]. As a result, in addition to the goods-leisure choice, the individual determines the value of active labour market participation in a dynamic optimization framework including search costs and the possibility of being unemployed [Möller and Aldashev, 2006]. The reservation wage is expected to respond negatively to an increase in search costs, and consequently, in the probability of being unemployed.

Nevertheless, the effect of future wages and prices is ambiguous depending on the income and substitution effect. The increases in future wage have a negative income effect on current labour supply, decreasing the reservation wages. The substitution effect is ambiguous depending on the utility function, positive if the leisure today and in the future are complements and negative if the utility function is additively separable. In order to estimate w^e and p^e we assume adaptive expectations and we use the Koyck transformation [see Lucas Jr and Rapping, 1969]. This is the way in which the wage dynamics and the path dependence of the participation appear in the labour equation.³

For convenience we assume a logarithmic functional form and choose p as a deflator, as a result we obtain a dynamic labour supply function such as:⁴

$$L_t^s = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln \left(\frac{w_t}{p_t} \right) + \beta_2 \ln \left(\frac{w_{t-1}}{p_{t-1}} \right) + \beta_3 \ln \left(\frac{p_t}{p_{t-1}} \right) + \beta_4 \ln L_{t-1}^s \quad (6)$$

We are aware that labour market equilibrium also depends on firms' behaviour; therefore, the labour demand and a wage setting equation should be included. In the standard search and matching framework, [Mortensen and Pissarides, 1994], wages are the outcome of a bilateral bargain between unmatched jobs and workers; thus wages are revised continuously in the face of productivity shocks. Nevertheless, in this kind of framework, the labour supply is fixed and exogenous. For this reason, and due to the inexistence of dynamic female labour-participation in a macroeconomic framework, it is beyond the scope of this paper to estimate a structural model. Accordingly, we will estimate an unrestricted equation while also taking into consideration additional variables suggested in the literature. However, the GMM allows us to account for the endogeneity of some variables as wages.

Perhaps the first important example of macro estimates of labour-force participation is the one found in Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969]. In this model the main determinant of the labour-force participation is the consumption wage. Labour-force participation increases in the current real wage as it fluctuates relative to its long run equilibrium level, i.e. labour force participation is a func-

³ Following Clark and Summers [1982], the wage dynamics and the path dependence of the participation arise directly from the utility function, since both past and future experience are included in the utility function.

⁴ Both Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969] and Clark and Summers [1982] consider that the interest rate and the asset effect on labour supply is negligible. Therefore it is not included in the final version of the labour supply function.

tion of the real wage, its lagged value and the lagged value of participation.⁵ Note however that Lucas and Rapping do not take into account ‘involuntary’ unemployment. As Clark and Summers [1982] point out, the choice not to include the unemployment rate is problematic for several reasons. First, the model would not provide an explanation for the fluctuations in the participation rate unrelated to observed employment fluctuations. Second, individual decisions regarding the labour supply will be affected by the knowledge that search costs are higher when unemployment is higher. As can be seen in the search models, [Andolfatto, 1996, Möller and Aldashev, 2006], the reservation wage responds negatively to an increase in search costs. Consequently, unemployment discourages the labour supply.

Pissarides [1991] departs from the Lucas-Rapping framework. Nevertheless, he takes into account the possibility that ‘involuntary unemployment’ could discourage labour market participation. He considers that the participation rate is determined by the action of people of working age, given the prospects for employment, i.e. the probability that a person will find work within a short period of time. In order to capture this phenomenon he includes the employment rate in the participation equation. Other authors such as Jaumotte [2004] or Genre et al. [2010] attempt to capture the prospects of employment by using the unemployment rate instead of the employment rate.⁶

Furthermore, Jaumotte [2004] allows for the so-called ‘added worker’ effect for female labour force participation, according to which a high male unemployment rate may stimulate female participation, i.e. individuals take into account not merely their own prospects of employment but also the prospects in which they act as a member of a couple. The argument is that women join the labour force in order to compensate for the loss of family revenue due to their husband’s unemployment.

2.2 Female labour-force participation

Although this specification of labour-force participation has been much used in the macroeconomic models, the literature has long maintained that female behaviour in the labour market has some special characteristics. For instance, Mincer [1962] indicates that women do not simply choose between leisure and labour but rather among leisure, labour and home production of goods and services.⁷ As a consequence, additional variables should be taken into account when looking for the determinants of female participation in the labour market. Most papers have limited themselves to analysing partial relationships, i.e. looking at the relationship between female participation and fertility and/or

⁵ Some authors such as Pissarides [1991] have included the gender wage gap, instead of real wages, for the labour-force equation.

⁶ The unemployment rate is also expected to capture the cyclical labour market pressures better than other business cycles.

⁷ From that point of view, home production is crucial to explain women’s weaker attachment to the labour market as home production is often regarded as a better alternative to market production for women than for men.

female education. Nevertheless, in recent years Jaumotte [2004] and Genre et al. [2010] have analysed female labour force participation by taking into account a more general framework which does not merely consider women's preferences but also takes labour-market institutions into account.⁸ Jaumotte focuses mainly on institutions aiming to reconcile motherhood and professional life, while Genre et al. concentrate on labour-market institutions.

The 'family-friendly institutions' analysed by Jaumotte [2004] are child benefits, childcare subsidies, and parental leave. Although child benefits could reduce poverty in families, they generate an income effect that could reduce the female labour supply. Thus, from a point of view of encouraging the female labour supply a better alternative would be childcare subsidies since they increase the return on market work⁹ The provision of paid parental leave also tends to boost female labourforce participation, by helping women to reconcile work and family life and strengthening their attachment to the labour market through a job guarantee.

Jaumotte [2004] also points out the importance of flexible working arrangements in helping to ensure that women with children are able to pursue a working career. Thus, increasing the availability of part-time work opportunities also tends to raise female participation.¹⁰ She also stresses the importance of a more neutral tax treatment of the work incentives of second earners compared with single earners to boost female participation by increasing the return on married women's market work.¹¹

Although Genre et al. [2010] have also taken into account variables aimed at reconciling motherhood and professional life, they emphasise the importance of labour-market institutions for female labour-force participation. They base themselves on Nickell and Layard [1999] or Blanchard and Wolfers [2000] who have highlighted the importance of the effect of labour market institutions on aggregate employment and unemployment. Genre et al. [2010] argue that changes in rules or features that increased the overall flexibility of labour market institutions have generally supported female labour-force participation.

However, although these recent papers show a more general framework for explaining female labour-force participation, taking into account not just women's preferences but also the relevant institutions, none of them award due

⁸ Mention should also be made of Pissarides et al. [2005], Bassanini and Duval [2009] and Bertola et al. [2007], who nevertheless focus on the female employment rate instead of the female participation rate.

⁹ Childcare subsidies reduce the relative price of formal childcare and, therefore, increase the relative return of market work. Nevertheless, their effectiveness could be reduced if women substitute formal for informal childcare

¹⁰ Nevertheless, as she also said, part-time work could entail a wage penalty, low social security coverage, job insecurity, and little training, i.e. it could risk marginalising women in these jobs.

¹¹ The tax system imposes excessive distortions on the labour supply decisions of married women relative to those of men and single women. Optimal taxation implies that the total deadweight loss of the tax system is reduced if marginal tax rates are lower for those individuals whose labour supply is more elastic to tax rates [Boskin and Sheshinski, 1983]. The relevant marginal tax rate for a married women are effectively taxed more heavily than for men and single women, providing scope for a move to neutrality.

consideration to earlier literature on participation in the labour market such as the work Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969]. There is a tendency to overlook the question of dynamics in labour markets, and the situation in which an individual's decision to participate is based not only on current wages and prices but also on expected wages and prices is neglected. Additionally, an increase in wages has been shown to have a different effect on the decision to participate depending on whether an individual considers that the job opportunity will be permanent or transitory.¹² It is also important to take into account the persistence or path-dependency of female labour-force participation. According to the arguments in Clark and Summers [1982], previous employment experience affects the current decision regarding participation. Several explanations for such phenomena are discussed in the literature. First, the question of human capital aspects has been addressed. As Clark and Summers [1982] indicate, those who are employed tend to accumulate more human capital (on-the-job training) which raises the return on work in the future relative to leisure. Second, individuals may be affected by peer group effects. As Vendrik [1998] shows, a woman's (non-) participation preferences are reinforced by the (non-) participation behaviour displayed by other women in her social reference group.¹³ Thus, when estimating the determinant of the female labour-force participation, attention should be paid to the dynamics in the labour market. As we will see, taking dynamic relations into account has some non-trivial consequences for the empirical results.

3 The empirical framework

One of the problems which arise at an aggregate level is that we do not examine homogeneous individuals. At the very least, we should take into account that the effect of some variables on female labour-force participation differs by age. For example, fertility decisions are crucial for prime-age women but irrelevant for those of a more advanced age and for young women still in full-time secondary or higher education. In order to address this issue, Jaumotte [2004] focuses only on prime-age women, while Genre et al. [2010] estimate three groups of women separately. We focused only on prime-age women (women from 25 to 54 years) and prime-age men, but we extended our specification to the whole female and male sample in order to assess the robustness of the results.

¹² Friedman [1962] was the first to distinguish between the permanent-transitory wage rate when studying the supply of labour. Transitory and temporary effects have also been analysed for the supply of married women [Mincer, 1962, Cain, 1966, Cain and Mincer, 1969]

¹³ Although, the peer effects are more important in the long run, they might play a significant role in the short run reinforcing or diminishing the added-worker effect under a negative shock.

3.1 The data

For most of the variables, we used data from the OECD. Their definitions are detailed in Appendix A. In some cases, however, calculations were needed, which are explained in this section. Moreover, in order to allow a better understanding of their possible effects, they are classified according to whether they affect mainly the supply-side (women's preferences to work), the demand-side (potential jobs available to women) or both, in the above order.

Supply-side

- *Education*: Education is closely associated with preferences, particularly for women, since women with higher education are more likely to have preferences biased toward market production. Highly educated women have a greater opportunity cost of non-working because they have made a more significant investment in human capital. Nevertheless, this variable is likely also to capture the high potential wages associated with high human capital. Our measure of education focused on the population aged 25 or more with tertiary education completed. We used the data from Barro and Lee [2001] for the period until 2000. In order to extend it up to 2010 we followed the methodology of their paper.

$$h_{3t} = \frac{H_{3t}}{L_t} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{L25_t}{L_t} \right) \right] h_{3,t-5} + \left(\frac{L25_t}{L_t} \right) HIGH_{t-5},$$

where, h_{3t} is the ratio of tertiary education attained at time t ; $L25_t$ the population aged 25-29 at time t , L_t , the overall population aged 25 and above at time t , $HIGH_{t-5}$ the gross enrolment rate at time $t - 5$ and H_{3t} the number of persons aged 25 and over for whom tertiary education is the highest level of schooling attained at time t . The data of the population by age and sex are from OECD and the gross enrolment ratio is taken from UNESCO. In order to check the robustness of our calculations we compared the trend of our estimations with the trend of the OECD data. There were no significant differences.

- *Fertility*: Traditionally, women must choose between the time dedicated to housework, highly correlated with the number of children, and the time dedicated to paid-work. These two variables have been negatively correlated over time. However, the most recent evidence does not support such a correlation for various countries, pointing to the role of work-family conciliation policies as a means of avoiding this trade-off. Genre et al. [2010] validated the existence of a positive relationship between participation and fertility for Sweden, Denmark and the Netherlands, while the relationship was negative for the rest of Europe.
- *Labour tax*: Labour taxes are also expected to play a role in determining women's participation. Any increase in taxes leading to lower net wages will tend to increase participation in order to keep the income level constant. We calculate the labour taxes following Nickell [2006]:

$$\frac{ESS}{(IE - ESS)},$$

with ESS equal to employers social security contributions (data available at the OECD National Account) and IE equal to total compensation for employees (Data available at the OECD Revenue Statistics)

- *Part-time jobs*: It has been argued that flexible working arrangements help to reconcile motherhood with professional life and, as a result, to ensure that women with children are able to pursue a working career. Jaumotte [2004] and Genre et al. [2010] assert that part-time employment is a relevant variable for explaining the increase in female labour-force participation.
- *Unemployment benefit system*: The existence of a generous unemployment benefit system could be seen as a positive incentive to participate in the labour market [Nickell and Layard, 1999]. Unemployment benefits may be described by two variables: the *income replacement ratio* (the amount of the benefit) and *benefit duration* (the length of time for which the benefit is available). We construct the *Benefit duration index* following Nickell [2006], that is, the index captures the level of benefits available in the later years of a spell relative to those available in the first year:

$$0.6 * \frac{brr23}{brr1} + 0.4 * \frac{brr45}{brr1}$$

where *brr1* is the benefit replacement rate for the first year, *brr23* the benefit replacement rate for the second and the third year, and *brr45* the benefit replacement rate for the fourth and fifth year [see Martin, 1996, for more details]. We used data from the William Nickell dataset for the period until 2003 and then extended it up to 2007, calculating *brr1*, *brr23* and *brr45* using the OECD Tax-Benefit Models. To assess the robustness of the calculation we compared our calculations with the benefit unemployment replacement rate from the OECD. No significant differences were observed.

Demand-side

- *Employment Protection Legislation (EPL)*: This indicator measures the procedures and costs involved in dismissing individuals or groups of workers and the procedures involved in hiring workers on fixed-term or temporary work agency contracts. The employment protection legislation raises the cost of employment adjustments, i.e. it tends to reduce the separation rate from employment into unemployment, and reduce the exit rate from unemployment into work as firms become more cautious about hiring [Nickell and Layard, 1999]. This will tend to reduce short-term unemployment and raise long-term unemployment. Nevertheless its effect on labour-force participation is not clear. We use the OECD summary indicator of the stringency of Employment Protection Legislation. Since this indicator starts in 1985, we extended it back as far as 1982 using data from Bassanini and Duval [2006].

- *Product market regulation*: This indicator summarises regulatory provisions in seven non-manufacturing sectors: telecoms, electricity, gas, postal services, rail transport, air passenger transport, and road freight. Excessive regulations of the service market could hamper the development of these sectors and limit the creation of employment opportunities. This may be especially important for employment of women, as women tend to be predominantly employed in the service sector [Pissarides et al., 2005]. The data were obtained from OECD (2011), Product Market Regulation Database

Supply and demand-side

- *Maternity leave (in weeks)*: Parental leave helps women to reconcile work and family life. The job security dimension also strengthens the continuity of their attachment to the labour market, though negative effects on hiring cannot be excluded. We define this variable as the length of paid maternity leave a mother could obtain in a particular country. We used data from Gauthier and Bortnik [2001] for the period until 2000 and extended it using the OECD Family database on www.oecd.org/els/social/family/database, but using the same criterion as Gauthier and Bortnik [2001].
- *Unions*: Unions' wage bargaining leads to higher wage compression and larger employment differences between insiders and outsiders. This discourages outsiders' in this case, women's - expectations of finding a job. Furthermore, in some earlier studies, unions were analysed as a source of discrimination by authors such as Becker [1957] and Ashenfelter [1972], although the results were not significant.

3.2 The dynamic panel model

In this paper we estimate a dynamic panel model. Within this class of models, the fixed effects specification is a common choice for macroeconomic analysis. It is believed to be more appropriate than a random effects model for two reasons. First, if the individual effect represents omitted variables, it is likely that these country-specific characteristics are correlated with the other regressors. Second, a typical macro panel is not likely to be a random sample from a larger universe of countries.

Let us then consider a dynamic fixed effects model:

$$y_{it} = \delta y_{i,t-1} + x'_{it}\beta + u_{it}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \quad t = 1, \dots, T \quad (7)$$

where y is the dependent variable, δ is a scalar, the regressor vector x'_{it} is $1 \times K$ and β is $K \times 1$. We will assume that the fixed effect u_{it} follows a one-way error component model

$$u_{it} = \mu_i + v_{it} \quad (8)$$

where $\mu_i \sim IDD(0, \sigma_\mu^2)$ and $v_{it} \sim IDD(0, \sigma_v^2)$, independent of each other and among themselves.

The inclusion of a lagged dependent variable in this model renders the OLS estimator biased and inconsistent.¹⁴ Since y_{it} is a function of μ_i , it immediately follows that $y_{i,t-1}$ is also a function of μ_i . Therefore, $y_{i,t-1}$ is correlated with the error term, even if the v_{it} are not serially correlated. As explained in Judson and Owen [1999], the econometric literature has dealt extensively with this problem. Their results, based on a Monte Carlo analysis, showed that for unbalanced panels: a) if $T = 30$, where T is the time dimension of the panel, the Least Square Dummy Variable (LSDV) performs just as well or better than the viable alternatives; b) when ≤ 10 , Arellano and Bond [1991]'s one-step Generalized Method of Moments estimator (AB GMM) is the best choice; c) when $T = 20$, AB GMM or Anderson and Hsiao [1982]'s estimator may be chosen. Subsequently, Blundell et al. [2001], reviewing developments to improve on the relatively poor performance of the standard one-step difference GMM estimator for highly autoregressive panel series, provided a Monte Carlo simulation comparison between one-step difference GMM and the estimator proposed in Blundell and Bond [1998], denoted as the GMM system. They showed that the GMM system, which relies on relatively mild restrictions on the initial condition process, has substantial asymptotic efficiency gains, as it not only greatly improves precision but also greatly reduces the finite sample bias. However, these GMM estimators were designed for panels where the number of individuals (N) is large and the number of time periods (T) is small. The finite sample properties of GMM estimators have been analysed by Blundell and Bond [1998], Soto [2006] and Hayakawa [2007]. Blundell and Bond [1998] show that the system GMM estimator can be considerably more efficient than difference GMM. The small sample bias of both estimators reduces when the autoregressive parameter is moderately high and the number of time-series observations is rather small (less than 10 periods). However, Blundell and Bond [1998] adopt $N=100$ as a definition of small sample, which is considerably above the number of countries in our sample. Soto [2006] uses Monte Carlo simulations to analyse the properties of various GMM and other estimators when the number of individuals is smaller ($N=100$; $N=50$; $N=35$), and the number of time periods is only moderately small ($T=12$). He finds that the GMM system estimator has the lowest bias and highest efficiency among the available alternatives. Hayakawa [2007] shows analytically why the system GMM estimator has these good small sample properties. Our sample is an unbalanced panel of 18 OECD countries¹⁵ from 1980 to 2007. We applied several tests and found that female participation has a unit root.¹⁶ Under

¹⁴ See Sevestre and Trognon [1985] for the magnitude of this asymptotic bias in dynamic error component models.

¹⁵ Countries included are Australia, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, the United Kingdom and the United States.

¹⁶ Applying the Fisher Test for the panel unit root using an augmented Dickey-Fuller test (2 lags) we were not able to reject the possibility that prime-age female labour-force participation, overall female labour-force participation, prime-age male labour-force participation and overall male labour-force participation contain a unit root at a level of 1%. Note that labour-force participation is bounded between 0 and 1, so a unit root would in principle

these conditions, the GMM system is not in principle applicable. Nevertheless, difference GMM is an even poorer choice, as explained in Bond et al. [2001]. These authors also argue that including time dummies or transforming variables into deviation from time means should be enough to satisfy stationarity conditions, since any arbitrary pattern in the time means is consistent with a constant mean of the transformed series for each country.¹⁷ Moreover, the GMM framework flexibly accommodates multiple endogenous variables.

As a consequence of these observations, our best available choice is the GMM system estimator by Blundell and Bond [1998]. Although this is a two-step estimator, under homoscedasticity of the v_{it} disturbances, the particular structure of the first-difference model implies that an asymptotically equivalent GMM estimator can be obtained in one step. Simulation studies have suggested very modest efficiency gains from using the two-step version, even in the presence of considerable heteroscedasticity. Furthermore, the dependence of the two-step weight matrix on estimated parameters makes the usual asymptotic distribution approximations less reliable for the two-step estimator.¹⁸ For this reason, we used a one-step estimator in this paper.

Moreover, we considered the useful advice provided by Roodman [2009b,a] in order to make appropriate specification choices. In particular, Roodman suggests: a) using orthogonal deviations instead of differences in order to minimize the gaps of the unbalanced panel [see Arellano and Bover, 1995]; b) putting every regressor into the instrument matrix: if a regressor is strictly exogenous, it is inserted as a single column; if it is predetermined but not strictly exogenous (such as our regressors), lags 1 and deeper are used in GMM-style; if it is endogenous, lags 2 and deeper are used in GMM-style; c) devoting considerable care in evaluating the results of autocorrelation and endogeneity tests, as a small number of cross-country observations makes the Arellano-Bond test for autocorrelation rather unreliable; furthermore, too many instruments weaken the power of Sargan and Hansen tests to detect overidentification; d) ‘collapsing’ the instrument set into a single column, in order to reduce excessive numbers of instruments. In this type of model the identification condition arises from the strict exogeneity of some of the explanatory variables (or the availability of strictly exogenous instrumental variables) conditional on the unobservable individual effects. For this reason, we also implemented the Arellano and Bond [1991] test for autocorrelation

make no sense. Nevertheless, in the 1980-2007 period, labour-force participation has risen considerably and may have been out of its steady-state path

¹⁷ Note that the assumption $E(\mu_i \Delta y_{i2}) = 0$ does not imply that the country-specific effects play no role in employment determination. The assumption means that there is no correlation between employment and the country-specific effect in the absence of conditioning on other variables.

¹⁸ Windmeijer [2005] proposes a finite-sample correction for the asymptotic variance of the two-step GMM estimator.

4 The results

As we explained in the previous section, the suitable estimator for our sample is Blundell and Bond [1998] system-GMM estimator.¹⁹ We applied robustness tests for all specifications, and we examined the behaviour of the coefficients and the overidentification test when the number of instruments included was reduced. For all specifications we obtained the same results independently of the number of the instruments used. Moreover, all estimations were checked using estimates based on OLS and within transformation procedures in order to appraise the robustness of the results.²⁰ The results for these robustness checks are shown in Appendix B.

In our specifications we included year dummies in order to allow for common shocks (inclusion of these dummies also makes the stationarity assumption more tenable), and country-idiosyncratic trends indicative of unobserved influences relating to female labour-force participation (Pissarides [1991] talks for instance of social attitudes towards female labour-force participation).

4.1 Static versus dynamic specification for female labour-force participation

In this section we carry out a dynamic versus static²¹ model comparison for five specifications of prime age labour-force participation of women ($l2554_t^f$) in order to assess the importance of the dynamic specification. We include one specification for each of the relevant authors from the background review: Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969], Pissarides [1991], Jaumotte [2004], Genre et al. [2010]. Additionally, we include an encompassing specification that takes into account the main contributions of each model. In Table 1, we present the results of the static and dynamic models for the five specifications as well as the number of observations and of instruments used, as well as the values of the Arellano-Bond AR(1), Arellano-Bond AR(2)²² and Sargan tests.

We started from the Lucas and Rapping framework where the real wage (w_t) is the most important variable. We included the wage deflated by the consumer index and its lag and we found a positive significant effect of these variables on female labour-force participation. Thus the Lucas and Rapping framework seems to be viable for female labour-force participation in both the

¹⁹ In order to test the endogeneity of the variables we used the difference-Sargan test for subgroups of variables. Real wage and the share of part-time jobs appear to be endogenous for female labour-force participation (both prime age women and women of working age) while none of the variables turn to be endogenous in the male equation.

²⁰ It is well known that OLS levels will give an estimate of δ that is biased upwards in the presence of individual-specific effects [see Hsiao, 1986, for example], and that within groups will give an estimate of δ that is seriously biased downwards in short panels [see Nickell, 1981]. Thus a consistent estimate of δ can be expected to lie in between the OLS levels and Within Groups estimates.

²¹ The static equation is estimated by using `xtivreg2` [Schaffer, 2010].

²² Within the Arellano and Bond [1991] procedure, AR(1) residuals are not detrimental to estimation, while AR(2) residuals are. None of our dynamic specifications show autocorrelation of second order and Sargan tests performed well in all of them.

static and the dynamic specification, the most important difference being the lower effect of prices p_t on female labour-force participation in the dynamic equation. We were also able to compute long-run elasticity with respect to the real wage. Our estimation of this model suggests a long-run wage elasticity of -0.04 (standard error (S.E.) = 0.010), i.e. essentially zero and consistent with Lucas and Rapping's results.²³

Since the wage and the lagged wage are significant with similar coefficients but opposite sign, in the encompassing equation we included the differenced and the current wage, in order to test for long-run effects. We also took into account the increase in prices to test for 'monetary illusion' effects.

Table 1 Labour-force participation for prime-age women: static versus dynamic models for Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969] and Pissarides [1991]

	Lucas and Rapping		Pissarides	
	Static ^a	Dynamic ^b	Static ^c	Dynamic ^d
w_t	0.374***	0.234***		
w_{t-1}	-0.323***	-0.236***		
w_t^{gap}			0.696**	0.009
Δp_t	0.217**	0.015		
em_t			0.158**	0.025
Δem_t			0.353***	0.492***
$l2554_{t-1}^f$		0.891***		0.899***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$		0.063		0.037
Constant		0.221***		0.179
Obs. (NT)	469	479	453	459
Countries (N)	18	18	18	18
Instruments	50	52	48	53
p-value AR(1)	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.009
p-value AR(2)	0.002	0.575	0.003	0.445
p-value Sargan	0.044	0.970	0.417	0.929
df Sargan	3	2	1	3

Notes: * p<0.1; **p<0.05; *** p<0.01. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.

^a Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus gdp, productivity, output gap and the increase of the employment growth

^{b, d} Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus 2 lags of the endogenous variables (collapse option used)

^c Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus productivity and unemployment rate

The second specification that we consider is Pissarides [1991]. For this author, it is not just the real wage but also the employment prospects that are important to the decision to participate in the labour market. Pissarides uses the employment rate (em_t) to capture this effect. For Pissarides, the only wage

²³ See Arellano and Bond [1991] for more details about long-run calculations. Standard errors are calculated using Delta method.

variable that turns out to be significant is the ratio of female to male wages (w_t^{gap}). We attempted to capture this effect but this variable did not appear to be significant. The increase in the employment rate was found to be significant and positive. In Pissarides's model, while the 'current' value of employment has an important role in the static specification, the employment difference takes its place in the dynamic specification. It can be readily agreed with Pissarides that it is important to take employment prospects into account. Nevertheless, several variables could account for this effect. The unemployment rate (u_t) could capture this effect better, as proposed by Jaumotte [2004], Genre et al. [2010]. Moreover, as mentioned earlier, Jaumotte [2004] considers that it is not merely the female (u_t^f) but also the male unemployment rate (u_t^m) that has effects on female participation in the labour market. Since these effects would go in opposite directions, we included the relative unemployment rate (u_t^{gap}) in the encompassing equation to show which effect dominates.²⁴

In the third specification (table 2), Jaumotte [2004] points out the importance of variables related to gender particularities in the labour market²⁵ such fertility, educational level (edu_t^f), flexible-working arrangements (part-time jobs), family-friendly institutions (maternity leave), sometimes also included with a quadratic specification to allow for non-linear effects. In our results, part-time jobs appeared to be important for explaining female participation, in both the static and the dynamic specification. Maternity leave also seemed to have a significant effect in the dynamic specification, although the direction of the relationship differs from the static specification and from Jaumotte [2004] and Genre et al. [2010].²⁶

Our results are similar to Ruhm and Teague [1997] and the duration of the leave was negatively associated with female participation. However, we continued to find a negative effect even after allowing for a non-linear relationship, i.e. for short periods of leave. An explanation could be that employers perceive parental leave as a negative consequence of hiring a female worker. Moreover, a long leave may have a discouraging effect on women's decision to participate, as suggested in the results obtained by Tanda [2001] for compulsory maternity leave.²⁷ We included female education and part-time jobs in the encompassing equation in addition to maternity leave and its square in order to analyse

²⁴ We calculated the relative unemployment rate as the male unemployment rate/female unemployment rate.

²⁵ We attempted to include other variables such as share of married women or share of parliament seats occupied by women but none of these variables appeared to be significant. Moreover, the sample diminished substantially.

²⁶ This variable is difficult to measure, and there is no commonly agreed definition. Genre et al. [2010] used the length of leave allowed for each woman; Jaumotte [2004] considered the maximum leave in any sector and OECD calculated the leave taking into account whether mothers received 100% of their wages or not. Results differed according to the definition of leave.

²⁷ Additional 'family-friendly institutions' would include childcare benefits or public childcare spending, although none of these appear to be significant. This could be attributable to lack of data, since it is difficult to find valid data and the series are too short. We do not list these estimations because the variables in question considerably reduce the sample.

Table 2 Labour-force participation for prime-age women: static versus dynamic model for Jaumotte [2004], Genre et al. [2010] and the Eclectic specification

	Jaumote		Genre et al.		Eclectic specification	
	Static ^a	Dynamic ^b	Static ^c	Dynamic ^d	Static ^e	Dynamic ^f
w_t					-0.047	-0.001
Δw_t					0.043	0.107***
w_t^f			0.063	-0.007*		
Δp					0.270***	0.229***
u_t			-0.040***	-0.012**		
u_t^m	0.013	-0.030***				
u_t^f	-0.052*	0.015				
u_t^{gap}					-0.061***	-0.009
Δu_t^{gap}					0.035**	-0.036*
$parttime_t$	0.122***	0.018*	0.080***	0.005	0.087***	0.014*
edu_t^f	0.085***	0.012			0.053**	0.017**
$leave_t$	0.006	-0.026*			0.024***	-0.008
$leave_t^2$	-0.002	0.010*			-0.009***	0.004
$fertility_t$	-0.108***	-0.024	-0.146***	-0.027	-0.036	-0.026*
$taxL_t$	-0.001	-0.001	0.006*	-0.001		
EPL_t	-0.009	-0.003	0.004	0.003		
PMR_t	0.009**	-0.002				
$grr - ub_t$			-0.044***	-0.007*	-0.001	-0.003
$duration - ub_t$			-0.010	-0.006	-0.034***	0.003
$union_t$			0.041	-0.000		
$l2554_{t-1}^f$		0.652***		0.775***		0.741***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$		0.171***		0.117		0.145
Constant		0.711***		0.494***		0.394**
Obs (NT)	409	431	341	413	424	448
Countries (N)	18	18	18	18	18	18
Instruments	59	62	48	56	59	61
p value AR(1)	0.002	0.037	0.003	0.000	0.0002	0.023
p-value AR(2)	0.003	0.609	0.014	0.891	0.001	0.741
p-value Sargan	0.498	0.110	0.605	0.501	0.022	0.128
df Sargan	2	7	1	2	1	2

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$. Year dummies and country-trends are included
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

^a Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus lagged unemployment (2 lag) and fertility (3 and 4 lags)

^b Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus two lags of the endogenous variables (collapse option used)

^c Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus productivity, output gap and lagged employment (4 lag)

^{d,f} Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus one lag of the endogenous variables (collapse option used)

^e Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus gdp, lagged gdp and output gap.

how our model performs when the wage and unemployment adjustments are included.

The last specification included is from Genre et al. [2010].²⁸ These authors point out the importance of taking into account certain institutions in the labour-markets such as labour taxes, employment protection legislation (EPL), unemployment benefit replacement rates, unemployment benefit duration indexes, union density, in order to gain greater insight into female labour-force participation. Most of the variables turned out to be non-significant, and those which did appear to be significant show no more than a small effect. The only labour-market institution that seemed to affect labour-force participation is unemployment benefits: the replacement rate ($grr - ub_t$). In both the static and the dynamic specification, always had a negative impact.²⁹ In the eclectic specification we include the replacement rate and duration ($duration - ub_t$) of the unemployment benefit.

Consistently with Genre et al. [2010] labour taxes $taxL_t$ seemed to have a positive effect on female participation in the static specification, i.e. higher taxes leading to lower net wages increase participation in order to maintain the income level constant [Nickell and Layard, 1999]. In the dynamic specification, however, neither the tax burden of the second earner [Jaumotte, 2004, Genre et al., 2010]. nor the tax wedge [Nickell and Layard, 1999] appeared to be significant. This could be due to a relationship driven by opposite forces. On the one hand, an increase in taxes could decrease labour-force participation since the net wage would be lower. On the other hand, any increase in taxes leading to lower net wages will tend to increase participation in order to keep the income level constant [Nickell and Layard, 1999]. None of the other labour-market institutions (in particular, employment protection legislation EPL_t) had a definite effect on female labour-force participation.

Finally, in the eclectic specification, we take into account not merely the dynamics of female labour-force participation but also of wages and unemployment. As described above, we included some variables that took into account women's preferences and labour-market institutions. Our results show that wage and unemployment dynamics are important for explaining female labour-force participation. Perhaps the main difference between the static and the dynamic specification, as well as in comparison to Jaumotte and Genre et al.'s (static) estimates, is the significant role of wages in the dynamic equation. After adjusting the model using the variables relating to gender particularities in the labour market in the 'eclectic' specification, we obtained a long-run wage elasticity of -0.02 (S.E. = 0.029), i. e. it appears to be inelastic as in the Lucas and Rapping model. Additionally, we were able to compute long-run elasticity with respect to the relative unemployment rate, obtaining -0.02 (S.E. =

²⁸ They performed several estimations for prime-age female participation. In contrast, we use the equation that focuses on the labour institutions, since this is the cited authors main contribution.

²⁹ The unemployment benefit could have a positive effect since more generous unemployment benefit systems represent a positive incentive to participate in the labour market.

0.102), i.e. the gap in the unemployment rates between men and women has no effect on long-run female labour-force participation.

The time flexibility arrangements captured by the share of part-time contracts, the share of women with tertiary education, and the fertility rate also appeared to be important, while the same cannot be said for maternity leave (at least if only the duration of leave is taken into account). Note that the latter variable has a positive and significant effect in the static model, but this effect basically disappears in the more highly structured dynamic model.

As can be seen from Appendix B (table 5-9), the Sargan test showed quite high values when too many instruments were included. As Roodman [2009b] indicates, too many instruments can overfit endogenous variables, failing to expunge their endogenous components, biasing coefficients and reducing the power of the Sargan test. With a reduction in the number of instruments, the value of the Sargan test decreased. However there was no change in the value and significance of the coefficients, indicating that our System GMM was valid.

Finally, in the dynamic equation, no labour-force institution turned out to be consistently significant, shedding some doubt on the robustness of the results reached in previous static estimates.

Based on these results, the present study assessed the performance of an 'eclectic' equation in explaining labour-force participation.³⁰ We applied this specification to all women of working age, as well as assessing its potential for explaining male participation. Finally, we performed various additional robustness checks, along the lines of those made in Bassanini and Duval [2006], and carried out a predictive exercise for the values of female labour-force participation from 2007 to 2010.

4.2 Dynamic specification for female labour-force participation

In Table 3, we show the results of the following categories: prime-age women, all women of working age, prime-age men and all men of working age. As can be seen, the results were quite similar over the different age ranges, but important differences between men and women can be observed.

³⁰ In this eclectic equation we did not include maternity leave and unemployment benefit since they do not appear to be significant in the encompassing equation.

Table 3 System-GMM for labour-force participation

	Prime-age women ^a	Women in working age ^b	Prime-age men ^c	Men in working age ^d
w_t	-0.002***	-0.002***	0.002	0.002
Δw_t	0.186***	0.361***	0.052***	0.228***
Δp_t	0.213***	0.332***	0.065**	0.223
u_t^{gap}	0.000	0.011	-0.001	0.008
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.039**	-0.039**	-0.001	-0.012
$parttime_t$	0.010***	0.021***	0.002**	0.014*
edu_t^f	0.011**	0.013*		
edu_t^m			-0.0004	0.004
$fertility_t$	-0.023**	-0.018***	0.0001	0.008
$young25_t$		-0.040		0.006
$old55_t$		0.008		0.010
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.806***			
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.116			
l_{t-1}^f		0.809***		
l_{t-2}^f		0.097		
$l2554_{t-1}^m$			0.647***	
$l2554_{t-2}^m$			0.057	
l_{t-1}^m				0.840***
l_{t-2}^m				-0.001
Constant	0.295***	0.406*	1.315	0.583
Obs (NT)	461	461	461	461
Countries (N)	18	18	18	18
Instruments	62	61	58	59
p value AR(1)	0.008	0.003	0.004	0.000
p-value AR(2)	0.497	0.974	0.993	0.963
p-value Sargan	0.119	0.371	0.346	0.924
df Sargan	7	4	3	3

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

^a Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus three lags of the endogenous variables (collapse option used)

^{b,c,d} Set of instruments: all exogenous variables plus two lags of the endogenous variables (collapse option used)

The real wage was an important variable for both male and female labour-force participation; however, the effect was much smaller for men than for women. For men it was the change in wages that was significant. As we showed earlier, the wage elasticity for prime-age women was inelastic -0.028 (S.E. 0.004) as was also the case for women in the working age -0.016 (0.004). Similarly, it was also inelastic for prime-age men 0.006 (S. E. 0.0004) and men in the working age 0.01 (S.E. 0.004). Although the coefficient showed a statistically significant difference from zero for prime-age men, its value was effectively close to zero. Interestingly, the rate of change in prices significantly affected female participation across various specifications, suggesting that women suffer from ‘monetary illusion’ to a greater extent than men.

Taking employment prospects into account [Pissarides, 1991], our results showed a negative effect of the relative unemployment rate for women, i.e. the added worker effect dominates the discouragement effect. This result confirms the importance of family income for the labour-force participation of women.

Summing up, female prime-age participation responds to the relative unemployment rate rather than to the overall unemployment rate. However, women are affected by the real wage of the economy instead of the relative wage, indicating that in this case women look at the overall situation and not at their relative position compared to men. Using the same argument, could the female unemployment rate have effects upon male labour-force participation? The answer is negative: a high level of female unemployment has no effects on male participation, implying that the added worker effect does not appear to be an important effect for men. Long-run elasticity with respect to the relative unemployment rate is not significantly different from zero either for men and women: prime-age women 0.001 (S.E. 4.744), women in the working age 0.12 (S.E. = 0.004), prime-age men 0.002 (S.E. 0.024) and men in the working age 0.05 (S.E. 0.012).

Let us now turn to the variables related to gender particularities in the labour market. Fertility appears to be significant and negative for prime-age women and proves to be non-significant for all women in the working age. This could be explained by assuming that fertility is not a relevant variable for the younger and older women in the labour market. Traditionally, women had to choose between time dedicated to housework, highly correlated with the number of children, and time dedicated to paid work. Thus, these two variables have been negatively correlated over time, especially for prime-age women. Note, however, that the most recent evidence highlights the existence of various countries in which such a correlation is not supported, pointing to the role of work-family reconciliation policies in avoiding this trade-off. Genre et al. [2005] validated the existence of a positive relationship between participation and fertility for Sweden, Denmark and the Netherlands, while the relationship is negative for the rest of Europe. We also checked for changes in the relationship between fertility decisions and women's participation in the labour market over recent years, and we found the positive effect of fertility in Nordic countries. Finally, as was to be expected, fertility was non-significant for men.

Education had a positive and significant effect in both prime-age women and all women of working age. This variable was closely associated with preferences, particularly for women, since women with higher education are more likely to have preferences biased toward market production. Highly educated women have a higher opportunity cost of non-working because they have invested more in human capital. In contrast, the share of men with tertiary education does not appear to be a relevant variable for explaining male participation in the labour market.

Flexible working arrangements play a key role in helping women with children to pursue a working career. The share of workers employed on a part-time basis is the main variable accounting for this effect and it appears to be signifi-

cant and positive.³¹ This result is consistent with the emphasis that Jaumotte [2004] places on this variable. In our case, however, flexible-working arrangements are also relevant for explaining male labour force participation, although the effect is smaller than for women.

As a whole, these comparisons suggest that our eclectic specification yields a robust and informative representation of labour-force participation decisions, the main differences across gender and age making good economic sense. In the next section we describe the results of some additional robustness tests that we performed upon this specification.

4.3 Additional robustness tests

We would now like to show that the results for our eclectic equation (prime-age women equation in Table 3) do not depend on any special structure of our sample, i.e. on any particular combination of years and countries. To demonstrate this, we performed three additional robustness tests, to investigate whether in small country samples, one single country could significantly affect the estimated parameters. Thus the first additional robustness check performed on the eclectic specification was designed to detect possible changes in the results obtained by eliminating one country at a time and re-estimating the eclectic equation. The results show that none of the countries were found to drive our results for any of the variables included (see Figure 1).

In the second robustness check, we examined whether our results changed when time variations were introduced (table 4). To perform this test, we re-estimated the eclectic specification on sub-samples of the main sample taken in blocks of ten, seven and five consecutive years. We re-estimated all possible subsamples for each length of time³² and we show the average of the coefficients. The reason for estimating by blocks instead of random subsamples was to retain as much as possible of the dynamic structure of the data. The average of the coefficients (for ten, seven and five consecutive years) was only marginally different from the original. The most important difference concerns the price increase, since the coefficient was higher with a decreasing time period. This effect could be explained by suggesting that monetary illusion is more important in the short-run than in the long-run.

³¹ The share of workers employed in the services sector shows the same effect on female-labour force participation as the share of women with part-time jobs. These two variables are highly correlated and insignificant when included together in the estimation.

³² For example, the first subsample for the block of 10 consecutive years would be from 1980 to 1990, the second from 1981 to 1991, and so on until the last sub-sample from 1997 to 2007. 5 consecutive years estimations start in 1982, since most of the countries has missing values in the first 2 years (1980 and 1981).

Fig. 1 Sensitivity analysis by country

Table 4 Re-estimation of the eclectic specification for prime-age women on subsamples (blocks of years)

Variables	Original estimation		10 consecutive years		7 consecutive years		5 consecutive years	
	Coef.	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
w_t	-0.002	0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.001	0.002	-0.002	0.003
Δw_t	0.186	0.048	0.136	0.137	0.132	0.313	0.029	0.340
Δp_t	0.213	0.079	0.212	0.126	0.210	0.249	0.135	0.307
u_t^{gap}	0.0001	0.005	-0.006	0.012	-0.007	0.017	-0.010	0.032
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.039	0.016	-0.034	0.029	-0.028	0.028	-0.025	0.033
$parttime_t$	0.010	0.003	0.011	0.010	0.007	0.017	0.022	0.042
edu_t^f	0.011	0.005	0.006	0.010	0.008	0.014	0.015	0.020
$fertility_t$	-0.023	0.011	-0.015	0.027	-0.021	0.040	-0.002	0.069
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.806	0.104	0.780	0.087	0.723	0.119	0.660	0.138
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.116	0.080	0.137	0.074	0.190	0.115	0.258	0.139
Constant	0.291	0.173	0.328	0.091	0.353	0.144	0.328	0.171

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

We now proceed to show a third robustness check, investigating the extent to which the eclectic equation (the prime-age women equation in Table 3) predicts actual female labour-force participation for prime-age women throughout the 2000-2010 period (see Figure 2). We performed a post-sample static forecast for the period 2008-2010, i. e. we used actual values of the lags rather than forecasting them.³³ Since values from 2008-2010 were not included in our estimation, we have not estimated the time effects coefficients (γ_t) for the years 2008, 2009 and 2010. To include them in our prediction we calculated them on the basis of Greene [2002] formula: $\gamma_t = \bar{y}_t - b' \bar{x}_t$, where \bar{y}_t and \bar{x}_t are, respectively, the means of the dependent and independent variables, over country observations in the year t , and b' is the vector of coefficients (table 3). Clearly, the period in question, having been affected by the financial crisis, which had important effects on the labour market of some countries, provides a significant additional check on the robustness of our estimates. In Figure 2, it can be observed that the fitted values adjust quite well to the actual values of female labour-force participation for every country. We observed no persistent prediction errors for participation trends in most countries.³⁴

³³ For the period after 2008, the OECD does not provide data for the incidence of part-time jobs based on the national definition (the definition that we have been using in our database in order to obtain data from 1980). For this reason, we extrapolate the value of part-time jobs based on the national definition for 2008-2010 using the trend of the incidence of part-time jobs based on the common definition.

³⁴ In order to check the efficiency of our forecast [Granger and Huang, 1997] we applied the white noise Portmanteau (Q) test and Bartlett's periodogram based test. Neither test was able to reject the null hypothesis that the errors follow a white noise, and consequently our prediction does not show persistent errors.

Fig. 2 Actual and fitted values for the labour-force participation rate for prime-age women

5 Concluding remarks

In recent years, some papers have attempted to explain female labour-force participation by taking into account several peculiarities of female behaviour in the labour market. Nevertheless, they do not award sufficient attention to

the dynamic analysis of labour market participation begun with Lucas Jr and Rapping [1969]. In this paper, we have tried to bring together these two strands of the literature. We would like to emphasize the importance of the dynamic framework in the male and female participation rate: individuals do not base themselves on current values of prices and wages only, but also on past and future values. Taking this into account leads to considerable changes in the magnitude and significance of the effects estimated for various participation determinants.

Our dynamic specification suggests that real wage levels are a relevant variable for explaining female labour-force participation (less so for men, where only changes matter). More precisely, wages seem to have a permanent effect for female participation but not for men. This could mean that the conception of labour force participation as exogenous in macroeconomic models of the labour market may be an inappropriate assumption. We also detected a negative and significant effect of the male unemployment rate on female participation (added worker effect). This added worker effect does not appear to be important for men.

Taking into account female labour-market particularities, maternity leave appears to be insignificant and negative in the eclectic dynamic specification. Difficulties in measuring this kind of variable and the delay in the effect of the policy changes could explain this result.

Fertility, education and part-time jobs appear to be consistently significant. While the fertility rate³⁵ shows a negative effect on female labour-force participation, education and part-time jobs are found to be important policy tools capable of increasing female-labour force participation. However, this raises the issue of whether part-time work entails a wage penalty, low social security coverage, job insecurity, and little training, potentially marginalising women in such jobs.

Other labour-market institutions do not appear to be consistently significant in determining either female or male participation. Apparently, labour-market institutions matter more for unemployment or employment than for labour-force participation. This is an issue that has not been widely investigated in the literature, and upon which we have attempted to introduce some novel evidence. The only institutional variable which appears to be significant in some dynamic specifications is the unemployment benefit duration (for women). This negative effect can of course be easily rationalized by economic theory.

References

Theodore Wilbur Anderson and Cheng Hsiao. Formulation and estimation of dynamic models using panel data. *Journal of econometrics*, 18(1):47–82, 1982.

³⁵ Recall however the exception from the Nordic countries [already highlighted in Genre et al., 2010].

- David Andolfatto. Business cycles and labor-market search. *The american economic review*, 86(1):112–132, March 1996.
- Manuel Arellano and Stephen Bond. Some tests of specification for panel data: Monte carlo evidence and an application to employment equations. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 58(2):277–297, 1991.
- Manuel Arellano and Olympia Bover. Another look at the instrumental variable estimation of error-components models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 68(1):29 – 51, 1995. ISSN 0304-4076. doi: 10.1016/0304-4076(94)01642-D. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/030440769401642D>.
- Orley Ashenfelter. Racial discrimination and trade unionism. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 80(3):435–464, 1972.
- Robert J Barro and Jong-Wha Lee. International data on educational attainment: updates and implications. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 53(3):541–563, 2001.
- Andrea Bassanini and Romain Duval. The determinants of unemployment across oecd countries: Reassessing the role of policies and institutions. *OECD Economic Studies*, 42(1):7, 2006.
- Andrea Bassanini and Romain Duval. Unemployment, institutions, and reform complementarities: re-assessing the aggregate evidence for oecd countries. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy*, 25(1):40–59, 2009. doi: 10.1093/oxrep/grp004. URL <http://oxrep.oxfordjournals.org/content/25/1/40.abstract>.
- Gary S Becker. *The Economics of Discrimination*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, Illinois, 1957.
- Giuseppe Bertola, Francine D Blau, and Lawrence M Kahn. Labor market institutions and demographic employment patterns. *Journal of Population Economics*, 20(4):833–867, 2007.
- Olivier Blanchard and Justin Wolfers. The role of shocks and institutions in the rise of european unemployment: the aggregate evidence. *The Economic Journal*, 110(462):1–33, 2000.
- Richard Blundell and Stephen Bond. Initial conditions and moment restrictions in dynamic panel data models. *Journal of econometrics*, 87(1):115–143, 1998.
- Richard Blundell, Stephen Bond, and Frank Windmeijer. Estimation in dynamic panel data models: improving on the performance of the standard gmm estimator. In *Advances in Econometrics: Nonstationary Panels, Panel Cointegration, and Dynamic Panels*, volume 15. Emerald Group Publishing Limited, 2001.
- Stephen Bond, Anke Hoeffler, and Jonathan Temple. Gmm estimation of empirical growth models. Economics Papers 2001-W21, University of Oxford, 2001.
- Michael J. Boskin and Eytan Sheshinski. Optimal tax treatment of the family: Married couples. *Journal of Public Economics*, 20(3):281 – 297, 1983. ISSN 0047-2727. doi: 10.1016/0047-2727(83)90027-0. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0047272783900270>.

- Glen G Cain. *Married women in the labor force: an economic analysis*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1966.
- Glen G Cain and Martin D Dooley. Estimation of a model of labor supply, fertility, and wages of married women. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 84(4):S179–S199, 1976.
- Glen G Cain and Jacob Mincer. Urban poverty and labor force participation: Comment. *The American Economic Review*, 59(1):185–194, 1969.
- Kim B Clark and Lawrence H Summers. Labour force participation: timing and persistence. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 49(5):825–844, 1982.
- Sergio Destefanis and Giuseppe Mastromatteo. Assessing the reassessment: A panel analysis of the lisbon strategy. *Economics Letters*, 115(2):148 – 151, 2012. ISSN 0165-1765. doi: 10.1016/j.econlet.2011.12.035. URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0165176511005581>.
- Zvi Eckstein and Osnat Lifshitz. Dynamic female labor supply. *Econometrica*, 79(6):1675–1726, 2011.
- Zvi Eckstein and Kenneth I Wolpin. Dynamic labour force participation of married women and endogenous work experience. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 56(3):375–390, 1989.
- Marco Francesconi. A joint dynamic model of fertility and work of married women. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 20(2):336–380, 2002.
- Milton Friedman. *Price theory: A provisional text*. Aldine Chicago, 1962.
- Anne H Gauthier and Anita Bortnik. Comparative maternity, parental, and childcare database, version 2. *University of Calgary*, 2001.
- Veronique Genre, Ramón Gómez-Salvador, and Ana Lamo. 5. the determinants of labour force participation in the european union1. *Labour Supply And Incentives To Work In Europe*, page 195, 2005.
- Véronique Genre, Ramón Gómez Salvador, and Ana Lamo. European women: why do (n't) they work? 1. *Applied Economics*, 42(12):1499–1514, 2010.
- Clive WJ Granger and Ling-Ling Huang. Evaluation of panel data models: Some suggestions from time series. Technical Report Discussion paper 97-10, University of California, San Diego., 1997.
- William H Greene. *Econometric analysis*. Pearson Education, Inc., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, fifth edition edition, 2002.
- Kazuhiko Hayakawa. Small sample bias properties of the system gmm estimator in dynamic panel data models. *economics Letters*, 95(1):32–38, 2007.
- James J Heckman. Sample selection bias as a specification error. *Econometrica: Journal of the econometric society*, 47(1):153–161, January 1979.
- V Joseph Hotz and Robert A Miller. An empirical analysis of life cycle fertility and female labor supply. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 56(1):91–118, January 1988.
- Cheng Hsiao. Analysis of panel data, econometric society monograph no. 11. *New York, NY*, 1986.
- Florence Jaumotte. Labour force participation of women: empirical evidence on the role of policy and other determinants in oecd countries. *OECD Economic Studies*, 2003/2(9):51–108, 2004.

- Ruth A Judson and Ann L Owen. Estimating dynamic panel data models: a guide for macroeconomists. *Economics letters*, 65(1):9–15, 1999.
- Richard Layard, Stephen Nickell, and Richard Jackman. Unemployment, macroeconomic performance and the labour market, 1991, rev. 2005.
- Robert E Lucas Jr and Leonard A Rapping. Real wages, employment, and inflation. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 77(5):721–754, September–October 1969.
- John P Martin. Measures of replacement rates for the purpose of international comparisons: a note. *OECD Economic Studies*, 26(1):99–115, 1996.
- Jacob Mincer. Labor force participation of married women: a study of labor supply. In Universities-National Bureau, editor, *Aspects of labor economics*, pages 63–106. Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey, 1962.
- Robert Moffitt. Profiles of fertility, labour supply and wages of married women: A complete life-cycle model. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 51(2):263–278, 1984.
- Joachim Möller and Alisher Aldashev. Interregional differences in labor market participation. *Jahrbuch für Regionalwissenschaft*, 26(1):25–50, 2006.
- Dale T Mortensen and Christopher A Pissarides. Job creation and job destruction in the theory of unemployment. *The review of economic studies*, 61(3):397–415, 1994.
- Stephen Nickell. Biases in dynamic models with fixed effects. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*, 49(6):1417–1426, November 1981.
- Stephen Nickell and Richard Layard. Labor market institutions and economic performance. *Handbook of labor economics*, 3:3029–3084, 1999.
- Stephen Nickell and Luca Nunziata. Labour market institutions database. Technical report, Centre for Economic Performance, London School of Economics and Political Science, London, 2001.
- William Nickell. *The CEP-OECD institutions data set (1960-2004)*. Centre for Economic Performance, London School of Economics and Political Science, 2006.
- OECD. Product market regulation database, 2011.
- Christopher Pissarides, Pietro Garibaldi, Claudia Olivetti, Barbara Petrongolo, and Etienne Wasmer. Women in the labor force: How well is europe doing? In Tito Boeri, Daniela Del Boca, and Christopher Pissarides, editors, *Women at Work: an Economic Perspective*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK., 2005.
- Christopher A Pissarides. Real wages and unemployment in australia. *Economica*, 58(229):35–55, February 1991.
- D. Roodman. How to do xtabond2: An introduction to difference and system gmm in stata. *Stata Journal*, 9(1):86–136, 2009a. URL <http://www.stata-journal.com/article.html?article=st0159>.
- David Roodman. A note on the theme of too many instruments*. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 71(1):135–158, 2009b.
- Christopher J. Ruhm and Jackqueline L. Teague. Parental leave policies in europe and north america. *Gender and Family Issues in the Workplace*, 1997.

-
- Mark E. Schaffer. xtivreg2: Stata module to perform extended iv/2sls, gmm and ac/hac, liml and k-class regression for panel data models. Technical report, Boston College Department of Economics., 2010.
- T Paul Schultz. Testing the neoclassical model of family labor supply and fertility. *Journal of Human Resources*, 25(4):599–634, Autumn 1990.
- Patrick Sevestre and Alain Trognon. A note on autoregressive error components models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 28(2):231–245, 1985.
- Marcelo Soto. System gmm estimation with a small number of individuals. *Institute for Economic Analysis, Barcelona, mimeo*, 2006.
- P Tanda. Politiche sociali: Selettività e universalismo. *ISAE Report*, 2001.
- Maarten Vendrik. Unstable bandwagon and habit effects on labor supply. *Journal of economic behavior & organization*, 36(2):235–255, 1998.
- Frank Windmeijer. A finite sample correction for the variance of linear efficient two-step gmm estimators. *Journal of econometrics*, 126(1):25–51, 2005.

6 Appendix A: Database

- *Childcare benefits*: this measures the increase in household disposable income from child benefits (including tax allowances). We obtained the data from Bassanini and Duval [2006]).
- *Consumer price index*: This measures the average changes in the prices of consumer goods and services purchased by households. In most instances, the Consumer price index is compiled in accordance with international statistical guidelines and recommendations. However, national practices may depart from these guidelines, and these departures may have an impact on international comparability between countries. We use data from OECD (on line: <http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>).
- *Gross benefit replacement rates*: Average across the first five years of unemployment for two earnings levels, three family situations and three durations of unemployment. Data are obtained from the OECD (on line: www.oecd.org/els/social/workincentives)
- *Labour-force participation rate*: this represents active people as a percentage total population of the same age and sex. The economically active population (labour force) comprises employed and unemployed people. It is obtained from the OECD labour base (on line: <http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>)
- *Part-time share*: this represents people employed on a part-time basis as a percentage of the same age population. The full-time/part-time distinction with regard to the main job is made on the basis of a spontaneous answer given by the respondents in all countries, except for the Netherlands, Iceland and Norway where part-time and full time are determined on the basis of whether the usual number of hours worked are, respectively, fewer or more than 35, and for Sweden, where this criterion is applied to the self-employed as well. The data were taken from OECD. The definition of part-time work varies considerably across OECD countries, but three main approaches can be distinguished: i) a classification based on the worker's perception of his/her employment situation; ii) a cut-off (generally 30 or 35 hours per week) based on the usual number of working hours, with people who usually work fewer hours being considered part-timers; iii) a comparable cut-off based on actual hours worked during the reference week. We used data from OECD (on line: <http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>).
- *Product market regulation*: This indicator summarises regulatory provisions in seven non-manufacturing sectors: telecoms, electricity, gas, postal service, rail transport, air passenger transport, and road freight. This indicator covers sectors in which anti-competitive regulation tends to be concentrated, given that manufacturing sectors are typically lightly regulated and open to international competition in OECD countries. The range is 0,6 increasing in regulation. Data is obtained from OECD [2011], Product Market Regulation Database (www.oecd.org/economy/pmr).
- *Public expenditures on childcare*: : this measures public spending on formal day care and pre-primary school per child, in 1995 PPP-US\$. Data on

formal day care do not include tax expenditures (i.e., tax allowances and tax credits for childcare expenses) unless they are refundable. Spending on pre-primary school includes both direct and indirect i.e. transfers and payments to private entities expenditures. We used data from Bassanini and Duval [2006].

- *Relative marginal tax rate on second earners*: This is defined as the ratio of the marginal tax rate on the second earner to the tax wedge for a single-earner couple with two children earning 100% of APW earnings. It represents the share of additional income that goes into paying increased household taxes when a previously inactive spouse takes up a job. We used data from Bassanini and Duval [2006].
- *Tax wedge*: This is defined as the ex-post wedge computed from national accounts as the sum of the employment tax rate, the direct tax rate and the indirect tax rate. The main source is the CEPOECD Institutions Data Set (1960-2004) from Nickell [2006]. But the data from Ireland show missing values, and were replaced with data from Nickell and Nunziata [2001] in order to obtain a larger set of observations (the series were fairly homogeneous).
- *Total fertility rate*: This is defined as the average number of live births a woman would have by age 50 if she were subject, throughout her life, to the age-specific fertility rates observed in a given year. Its calculation assumes that there is no mortality. The total fertility rate is expressed as the number of children per woman. The data are taken from OECD (online: http://www.oecd.org/document0,3746,en_2649_201185_46462759_1_1_1_1,00.html)
- *Total labour cost*: Compensation of employees (COE) compiled according to the System of National Accounts 1993, adjusted for the self-employed by multiplying COE by the ratio of total hours worked by all people in employment to total hours worked by all employees of businesses. Concepts exclude the cost of employee training, welfare amenities and recruitment; taxes on employment (e.g. payroll tax) and fringe benefits tax. Time series were extended back to 1970 for most OECD Member countries linking the series with related historical time series made available to the OECD sometime in the past. Total labour costs for economic activities refer to G-K (Market Services) and C-K (Business Sector). We use data from OECD (on line: <http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>).
- *Total unemployment rate*: This represents unemployed persons as a percentage of same age and sex active population as a percentage of total population. Unemployed people are defined as people who were without work during the reference week, were currently available for work and were either actively seeking work in the past four weeks or had already found a job to start within the next three months. The data were obtained from OECD (on line: <http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>).
- *Union density*: Trade union density corresponds to the ratio of wage and salary earners who are trade union members, divided by the total number

of wage and salary earners. We use data from OECD (on line:<http://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx>).

7 Appendix B: Behaviour of the coefficients when we reduce the number of instruments. OLS and FE estimations as a control

Table 5 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, Lucas's specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	0.111***	0.145***	0.233***	0.234***	0.242***	0.247***	0.244***	0.251***
w_{t-1}	-0.113***	-0.162***	-0.235***	-0.236***	-0.244***	-0.249***	-0.247***	-0.253***
Δp_t	-0.004	0.100*	0.015	0.015	0.016	0.011	0.013	0.012
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.947***	0.797***	0.892***	0.891***	0.866***	0.842***	0.848***	0.862***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.012	-0.024	0.062	0.063	0.083*	0.102**	0.098**	0.086
Cons.	0.200***	1.053***	0.220***	0.221***	0.241***	0.262***	0.257***	0.245***
Obs.	479	479	479	479	479	479	479	479
Instr.			50	52	54	56	58	60
AR(1)			0.002	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002
AR(2)			0.561	0.575	0.749	0.904	0.864	0.767
Sargan			.	0.970	0.845	0.726	0.780	0.681
Sargan df			0	2	4	6	8	10

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 6 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, Pissarides's specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t^{gap}	0.012*	0.03	0.017	0.009	0.010	0.010	0.010	0.009
em_t	0.031	0.032	0.124	0.025	0.039	0.047	0.031	0.034
Δem_t	0.492***	0.458***	0.461***	0.492***	0.487***	0.485***	0.490***	0.489***
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.911***	0.801***	0.805***	0.899***	0.886***	0.878***	0.893***	0.891***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.023	-0.016	0.069	0.037	0.042	0.044	0.039	0.039
Cons.	0.164***	0.754***	0.018	0.179	0.155	0.143	0.168*	0.164*
Obs.	459	459	459	459	459	459	459	459
Instr			51	53	55	57	59	61
AR(1)			0.031	0.009	0.006	0.005	0.004	0.004
AR(2)			0.754	0.445	0.483	0.496	0.454	0.456
Sargan			0.609	0.929	0.924	0.981	0.899	0.767
Sargan df			1	3	5	7	9	11

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 7 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, Jaumotte's specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
<i>parttime_t</i>	0.011*	0.050***	0.014*	0.018*	0.019**	0.019**	0.018**	0.017**
<i>taxL_t</i>	0.000	0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
<i>leave_t</i>	-0.012**	-0.014	-0.020	-0.026*	-0.027*	-0.028*	-0.027*	-0.025*
<i>leave_t²</i>	0.005***	0.004	0.008	0.010*	0.010**	0.011**	0.010**	0.010*
<i>EPL_t</i>	-0.005	-0.007	-0.004	-0.003	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.003
<i>u_t^m</i>	-0.028***	-0.044***	-0.029**	-0.030***	-0.034***	-0.035***	-0.033***	-0.030**
<i>u_t^f</i>	0.025***	0.038***	0.017	0.015	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.016
<i>edu_t^f</i>	0.003	0.042**	0.008	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.011	0.011
<i>fertility_t</i>	-0.005	-0.031*	-0.023	-0.024	-0.030	-0.028	-0.028	-0.024
<i>PMR_t</i>	-0.001	0.002	-0.001	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002	-0.001
<i>l2554_{t-1}^f</i>	0.809***	0.586***	0.746***	0.652***	0.641***	0.623***	0.643***	0.659***
<i>l2554_{t-2}^f</i>	0.101	0.034	0.111*	0.171***	0.183***	0.192***	0.180***	0.171***
Cons.	0.357***	1.356***	0.583***	0.711***	0.712***	0.745***	0.715***	0.690***
Obs.	431	431	431	431	431	431	431	431
Instr.			58	62	66	70	74	78
AR(1)			0.026	0.037	0.035	0.025	0.020	0.021
AR(2)			0.945	0.609	0.553	0.466	0.554	0.640
Sargan			0.306	0.110	0.004	0.005	0.010	0.007
Sargan df			3	7	11	15	19	23

Notes: * p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included.
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels.
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 8 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, Genre et al.s specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
<i>grr - ub_t</i>	-0.002	-0.019**	-0.007*	-0.005	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
<i>duration - ub_t</i>	-0.004	-0.001	-0.006	-0.006	-0.008**	-0.009**	-0.008**	-0.008**
<i>union_t</i>	-0.001	0.030	-0.000	-0.001	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
<i>EPL_t</i>	0.000	0.000	0.003	0.002	-0.003	-0.003	-0.002	-0.003
<i>taxL_t</i>	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
<i>u_t</i>	-0.004	-0.019***	-0.012**	-0.010*	-0.010*	-0.011**	-0.011**	-0.011**
<i>w_t^f</i>	-0.002	-0.059**	-0.007*	-0.005	0.001	0.000	-0.000	-0.000
<i>fertility_t</i>	-0.015	-0.074**	-0.027	-0.024	-0.029*	-0.032*	-0.032*	-0.032**
<i>parttime_t</i>	0.004	0.057***	0.005	0.005	0.010	0.011*	0.010*	0.010*
<i>l2554_{t-1}^f</i>	0.829***	0.586***	0.775***	0.771***	0.754***	0.723***	0.727***	0.726***
<i>l2554_{t-2}^f</i>	0.091	0.013	0.117	0.129	0.127	0.148*	0.145**	0.146**
Constant	0.353***	1.490***	0.494***	0.456***	0.501***	0.545***	0.542***	0.543***
Observations	413	413	413	413	413	413	413	413
Instruments			56	59	62	65	68	71
p value AR(1)			0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
p-value AR(2)			0.891	0.818	0.794	0.645	0.654	0.647
p-value Sargan			0.501	0.076	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
Sargan df			2	5	8	11	14	17

Notes: * p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included.
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels.
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 9 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, eclectic specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.002**	-0.001**	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Δw_t	0.100***	0.045	0.107***	0.075*	0.098**	0.115***	0.109**	0.106**
Δp_t	0.199***	0.179**	0.229***	0.122	0.200**	0.256**	0.239**	0.232***
u_t^{gap}	-0.007	-0.029*	-0.009	-0.005	-0.008	-0.010	-0.010	-0.009
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.040**	-0.017	-0.036*	-0.045**	-0.039**	-0.034*	-0.036*	-0.037**
$parttime_t$	0.013***	0.035**	0.014*	0.010**	0.013*	0.015*	0.014*	0.014**
$leave_t$	-0.003	-0.005	-0.008	0.006	-0.004	-0.011	-0.009	-0.008
$leave_t^2$	0.002	0.001	0.004	-0.002	0.002	0.005	0.004	0.004
$fertility_t$	-0.022	-0.045**	-0.026*	-0.015	-0.023*	-0.029*	-0.027*	-0.026*
$duration - ub_t$	-0.003	-0.005	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.004	-0.003	-0.003
$grr - ub_t$	0.002	-0.017**	0.003	-0.001	0.002	0.003	0.003	0.003
edu_t^f	0.012***	0.028	0.017**	0.007	0.014*	0.019**	0.017*	0.016**
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.797***	0.573***	0.741***	0.885***	0.769***	0.683***	0.714***	0.725***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.111	0.072	0.145	0.061	0.134	0.189*	0.169	0.162*
Constant	0.321***	1.350***	0.394**	0.209	0.339**	0.437***	0.402**	0.389***
Observations	448	448	448	448	448	448	448	448
Instruments			61	64	67	70	73	76
p value AR(1)			0.023	0.028	0.017	0.016	0.012	0.013
p-value AR(2)			0.741	0.340	0.563	0.854	0.929	0.870
p-value Sargan			0.128	0.092	0.089	0.143	0.251	0.265
Sargan df			2	5	8	11	14	17

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 10 Labour-force participation for prime-age women, eclectic specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	-0.002***	-0.003	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***
Δw_t	0.093**	0.052	0.218***	0.183***	0.186***	0.199***	0.189***	0.181***
Δp_t	0.191***	0.189***	0.198**	0.148	0.213***	0.227***	0.209**	0.198***
u_t^{gap}	-0.002	-0.027**	0.001	-0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	-0.000
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.044**	-0.015	-0.038**	-0.040**	-0.039**	-0.038**	-0.039**	-0.039**
$parttime_t$	0.012***	0.041***	0.010***	0.009***	0.010***	0.010***	0.010***	0.009***
edu_t^f	0.010***	0.040**	0.010**	0.006	0.011**	0.012**	0.011**	0.010**
$fertility_t$	-0.024	-0.039**	-0.020	-0.014	-0.023**	-0.025**	-0.022**	-0.021**
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.832***	0.612***	0.860***	0.911***	0.806***	0.784***	0.811***	0.824***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.091	0.052	0.072	0.041	0.116	0.133	0.113	0.104
Constant	0.292***	1.196***	0.261**	0.192	0.295***	0.318***	0.292***	0.279***
Observations	461	461	461	461	461	461	461	461
Instruments			56	59	62	65	68	71
p value AR(1)			0.020	0.022	0.008	0.005	0.005	0.005
p-value AR(2)			0.420	0.329	0.497	0.610	0.454	0.386
p-value Sargan			0.868	0.127	0.119	0.196	0.352	0.362
Sargan df			1	4	7	10	13	16

Notes: * p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included.
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels.
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 11 Labour-force participation for women in working age, eclectic specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	-0.002***	-0.003	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***	-0.002***
Δw_t	0.093**	0.052	0.218***	0.183***	0.186***	0.199***	0.189***	0.181***
Δp_t	0.191***	0.189***	0.198**	0.148	0.213***	0.227***	0.209**	0.198***
u_t^{gap}	-0.002	-0.027**	0.001	-0.002	0.000	0.001	0.000	-0.000
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.044**	-0.015	-0.038**	-0.040**	-0.039**	-0.038**	-0.039**	-0.039**
$parttime_t$	0.012***	0.041***	0.010***	0.009***	0.010***	0.010***	0.010***	0.009***
edu_t^f	0.010***	0.040**	0.010**	0.006	0.011**	0.012**	0.011**	0.010**
$fertility_t$	-0.024	-0.039**	-0.020	-0.014	-0.023**	-0.025**	-0.022**	-0.021**
$l2554_{t-1}^f$	0.832***	0.612***	0.860***	0.911***	0.806***	0.784***	0.811***	0.824***
$l2554_{t-2}^f$	0.091	0.052	0.072	0.041	0.116	0.133	0.113	0.104
Constant	0.292***	1.196***	0.261**	0.192	0.295***	0.318***	0.292***	0.279***
Observations	461	461	461	461	461	461	461	461
Instruments			56	59	62	65	68	71
p value AR(1)			0.020	0.022	0.008	0.005	0.005	0.005
p-value AR(2)			0.420	0.329	0.497	0.610	0.454	0.386
p-value Sargan			0.868	0.127	0.119	0.196	0.352	0.362
df Sargan			1	4	7	10	13	16

Notes: * p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included.
Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels.
Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 12 Labour-force participation for prime-age men, eclectic specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	0.002***	0.026***	0.009	0.002	0.002**	0.002**	0.002**	0.002**
Δw_t	0.052***	0.030*	0.021	0.052***	0.052***	0.052***	0.052***	0.053***
Δp_t	0.062***	0.042**	0.168	0.065**	0.068***	0.067***	0.068***	0.065***
u_t^{gap}	-0.001	-0.002	0.005	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.001	-0.000	0.006	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
$parttime_t$	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.002**	0.002*	0.002**	0.002*	0.002**
edu_t^m	0.000	0.007	0.043	-0.0004	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.0004
$fertility_t$	-0.000	-0.006	-0.007	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
$l2554_{t-1}^m$	0.663***	0.548***	-0.038	0.647***	0.633***	0.636***	0.628***	0.649***
$l2554_{t-2}^m$	0.061	0.026	-0.623	0.057	0.045	0.047	0.038	0.058
Constant	1.223***	1.685***	7.441	1.315	1.429**	1.412**	1.485**	1.301**
Observations	461	461	461	461	461	461	461	461
Instruments			56	58	60	62	64	66
p value AR(1)			0.697	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
p-value AR(2)			0.509	0.993	0.910	0.922	0.858	0.978
p-value Sargan			0.740	0.346	0.418	0.548	0.720	0.799
df Sargan			1	3	5	7	9	11

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.

Table 13 Labour-force participation for men in working age, eclectic specification

Variable	OLS	FE	Sys-GMM 1 lag	Sys-GMM 2 lags	Sys-GMM 3 lags	Sys-GMM 4 lags	Sys-GMM 5 lags	Sys-GMM 6 lags
w_t	0.002***	0.026***	0.009	0.002	0.002**	0.002**	0.002**	0.002**
Δw_t	0.052***	0.030*	0.021	0.052***	0.052***	0.052***	0.052***	0.053***
Δp_t	0.062***	0.042**	0.168	0.065**	0.068***	0.067***	0.068***	0.065***
u_t^{gap}	-0.001	-0.002	0.005	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
Δu_t^{gap}	-0.001	-0.000	0.006	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001
$parttime_t$	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.002**	0.002*	0.002**	0.002*	0.002**
edu_t^m	0.000	0.007	0.043	-0.0004	0.001	0.001	0.001	-0.0004
$fertility_t$	-0.000	-0.006	-0.007	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
$l2554_{t-1}^m$	0.663***	0.548***	-0.038	0.647***	0.633***	0.636***	0.628***	0.649***
$l2554_{t-2}^m$	0.061	0.026	-0.623	0.057	0.045	0.047	0.038	0.058
Constant	1.223***	1.685***	7.441	1.315	1.429**	1.412**	1.485**	1.301**
Observations	461	461	461	461	461	461	461	461
Instruments			56	58	60	62	64	66
p value AR(1)			0.697	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004
p-value AR(2)			0.509	0.993	0.910	0.922	0.858	0.978
p-value Sargan			0.740	0.346	0.418	0.548	0.720	0.799
df Sargan			1	3	5	7	9	11

Notes: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; ***. Year dummies and country-trends are included. Standard errors robust to heteroskedasticity and serial correlation within panels. Lower case variables are in logarithms.